

Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices Among Adult Malaria Patients Co-Infected with Opportunistic Intestinal Coccidian Parasites in Fundong Health District, Northwest, Cameroon: A Cross Section Study Design

Formbui Paul Atah

Department of Public Health and Hygiene, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Buea, Cameroon

Njunda Anna Longdoh

Department of Medical Laboratory Sciences, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Buea, Cameroon

Benjamin Pokam Thumamo

Department of Medical Laboratory Sciences, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Buea, Cameroon

Jane Francis Akoachere

Department of Microbiology and Parasitology, Faculty of Science, University of Buea, Cameroon

Suggested Citation

Atah, F.P., Longdoh, N.A., Thumamo, B.P. & Akoachere, J.F. (2023). Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices Among Adult Malaria Patients Co-Infected with Opportunistic Intestinal Coccidian Parasites in Fundong Health District, Northwest, Cameroon: A Cross Section Study Design. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(4), 1121-1140. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(4\).105](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(4).105)

Abstract:

Introduction: Malaria and intestinal coccidian parasitic co-infections, are becoming a public health emergency affecting millions of people around the world. They are among the leading cause of socio-economic problems, long suffering and death especially in developing countries like Cameroon. Introducing new appropriate preventive and control measures to the population requires thorough assessment of community and patient-based knowledge, attitude and preventive practices towards malaria and pathogenic intestinal coccidian parasites is crucial. Our study aimed to describe knowledge, attitudes, and practices and the risk factors among adult malaria patients co-infected with intestinal parasitic infections in the Fundong Health District, a locality in the Northwest Region of Cameroon. **Methods:** This was a cross-sectional study carried out

between February and December, 2022 involving sixteen (16) health facilities in Fundong Health district. A total number of 330 patients participated in the study. Normal saline wet mount and formol-ether concentration techniques were employed in coccidian parasitic detection. Blood samples were subjected to Giemsa stained and viewed microscopically to detect the *Plasmodium* parasites. Pretested structured questionnaires were administered to collect information on patient's socio-demographic factors and determine patients' knowledge, attitudes and practices towards malaria and intestinal coccidian parasites, as well as their prevention and control. The Pearson's Chi-Square (χ^2) and Student T-test were performed a part of the statistical analysis to check for associations between malaria, infection and between malaria-coccidian co-infection and demographic factors. Statistical significance was set a P-value < 0.05. **Results:** Participants main sources of information on malaria were: Television (TV) and radio 111/330 (34%), community health workers 109/330 (33%), and Hospitals (37%). Participants had good knowledge of mosquito bite as the malaria transmission route, 296/330 (90%), night time is the frequent biting time for the mosquito 296/330 (90%), dark corners 229 (69%) and dirty areas 175 (53%) as mosquito resting places. Knowledge score was also good on cleaning of the house surroundings, 281/330 (85%), clearing

the bushes 180/330(55%), poor knowledge score on drainage of stagnant water 113/330 (34%) as ways to prevent the mosquito from multiplying. Participants had good knowledge of insecticide treated bed nets 295/330 (89%) as the best way to prevent mosquito bites. However, participants also expressed poor knowledge on edges of the river or streams 7(20%), and animal shed 20/330 (6%) as mosquito hiding places, and *Plasmodium* specie as malaria causative agent 8/330 (2%) (P -value=0.011). Poor scores were recorded on knowledge of opportunistic intestinal coccidian parasites (19.4%) (P =0.427), and was significantly low on unsafe water (47.2%) (P -value=0.036) as possible transmission routes for coccidian parasites. The knowledge score was also low on the at-risk population for malaria and intestinal coccidian infection (31.9%) P -value=0.009. Participants who had poor knowledge about coccidian transmission routes were less likely to drink from protected water source with an odds of 0.713(95% CI: 0.297-1.711) P value=0.449, compared to those who were more knowledgeable and who were 2.981(95% CI: 1.367-6.115) P value=0.005, more likely to use protected source of drinking water. Participants who had hand washing facility in the household were 3.488 (1.760-6.912) value=0.001 times more likely have better knowledge of coccidian transmission routes compared to those who did not have 0.748 (95% CI: 0.406-1.376) P value=0.350. Poor knowledge score of poor hygiene as major cause of coccidian infection significantly associated with poor practice score of sometime or not at all disinfecting animal shed to prevent coccidian infection among study participants (P =0.039). **Conclusion:** The overall knowledge scores, attitude and practices level of participants towards malaria and opportunistic intestinal coccidian parasites were relatively good. A significant proportion of the participants still have misconceptions about cause, modes of transmission and practices towards malaria and coccidian prevention methods. A combined health education programmes for malaria and intestinal coccidian parasites aimed at raising community awareness needs to be evidence based and requires innovative approaches, to address the gaps identified in the study.

Keywords: *Malaria-coccidian co-infections, Knowledge scores, attitudes and practices, odds ratios, gaps, health education.*

Introduction

Malaria still remains a public health concern globally with Sub-Sahara Africa (SSA), bearing the greatest burden of the disease. Globally, in 2021, there were 249 million cases reported and 619,000 million deaths were registered, with 234 million cases and 593,000 deaths reported in the Africa region alone (World Health Organization, 2022). Cameroon lies within the endemic area of high malaria transmission, whereby everyone is at risk of malaria infection (Antonio-Nkondjio et al., 2019). In 2021 over 6.6 million cases of malaria were reported with a slight increase in incidence, with 13,839 deaths, a decrease from the 2020.

Malaria and intestinal parasites affects the poorest and impoverished communities in low and middle income countries. Nearly 50% of hospitalization and 22% of annual deaths in Cameroon are due to malaria (Mbohoun Nchetnkou, Kojom Foko, & Lehman, 2020).

Today intestinal parasites (IPs) are considered one of the most prevalent infectious diseases affecting mankind (Harhay, Horton, & Olliaro, 2010). The World Health Organization (WHO), reports that there are over 3 billion people worldwide who are infected with one or more intestinal parasitic diseases (WHO, 2022).

The overlapping infections have been reported (Njunda et al., 2016), and the risk of death is higher in patients with multiple infections of malaria and intestinal infections (CDC, 2021). There is evidence to support the integration of diseases (Standley et al., 2018) control and prevention in different settings. In Cameroon the national programme for the control of malaria and the national deworming programmes both committed to eradicate malaria and intestinal diseases however, this does not include intestinal diseases related to coccidian infection. Although runned parallel to each other, these efforts have kept malaria and

prevalence of intestinal parasites (PIPs) on a gradual decline. Malaria has witnessed a drop in prevalence over the past decade, largely due to the nationwide distribution of the long-lasting insecticides treated mosquitoes bed nets (LLITNs) (World Health Organization, 2022). The prevalence of PIPs also dropped from 33% to 27.8%, from 2006 to 2012 (Vouking et al., 2014) with lower rates in urban areas than rural. Recent studies on malaria co-infection with PIPs prevalence in Cameroon revealed 11.9% in rural setting and 3% in urban setting, clearly demonstrating the impact of knowledge on malaria and PIPs prevention and control. This shows behaviours are gradually changing as communities and individuals acquire more knowledge through health education that have continued to help them to adhere to control and prevention measures (Mekachie Sandie et al., 2021; Njunda et al., 2020).

Knowledge of the causes, modes of transmission and prevention of diseases such as malaria and pathogenic intestinal parasites have a key role in the modelling people's behaviours towards their prevention and control practices (Alharazi et al., 2020). Their understanding of knowledge, attitudes and practices towards malaria and PIPs control have improved over the years (Ming, & Huan, 2018). Some findings have revealed that poor knowledge, bad attitudes and poor practices towards a certain disease may be reluctant to implement some preventive measures and share information on the positive effects on the control of the diseases (Sazmand et al., 2020). The negative impact on individuals and communities are enormous, often resulting in the prevalence of bad practices such as self-medication, use of street drugs, low ability to seek medical care and high tendency to use traditional medicine, improper use and low frequency of sleeping under the insecticide treated bed-nets (ITNs). In some settings, environmental hygiene, faecal contamination of food, and drinking water, have been reported (Nsagha et al., 2016; Assob et al., 2012; Zvinorova et al., 2016; Same-Ekobe, 1997).

Knowledge of malaria co-infection with new emerging intestinal diseases such as those caused by coccidian parasites (Warren, 2009) is still very

low in many communities in Cameroon. This requires that health educational campaign need to be evidence based and adapted to address new emerging public health threats. This study aimed to investigate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of adult malaria patients suffering from multiple co-infections with intestinal coccidian parasites in the Fundong Health District (FHD) in Northwest region of Cameroon. The data generated will support evidence for innovative development of malaria-PIPs control strategies in Cameroon.

Study Site

The FHD is located between latitude 6° 4' and 6°23' to the North of the equator and longitude 10° and 10° 33' to the East of the Greenwich Meridian and its attitude ranges from (800-2500m) above sea level (Kamga et al., 2011). The FHD is located 80km to the North West Regional Capital city of Bamenda. Most of the settlements are rural (80%) with over 250,000 inhabitants who are mainly peasant farmers. Both men and women are involved in plantation and agricultural activities along the fertile slopes characteristic of the area. The Fulani men are involved are herdsman involved mainly in cattle raising in the occupying the hilly terrains that surrounds most of the area. It is found within the malaria high risk zones in Cameroon with moderate levels of transmission during and just after the rainy season which begins in March and ends in early October. Malaria prevalence in the region is 10% (MOH, 2018; National Institute of Statistic, Cameroon, 2022). The tropical climate makes it a favourable environment for the malaria vector to thrive. A vast majority of the population are poor, creating a favourable condition for intestinal diseases to thrive (World Bank, 2019). The prevailing poor hygiene and sanitation, as well as the low socio-economic status of the inhabitants, that exist in the region and Cameroon as whole, exposes the population to the risk of water borne infections and opportunistic parasitic diseases in particular (Nsoh et al., 2016).

Study Population

Only adult malaria patients who signed the informed consent and willingly accepted to be

tested for opportunistic intestinal parasites were recruited as participants for the study. Those who had been on antibiotics and anti-parasitic drugs two weeks prior to consultation were excluded from the study.

The Survey Questionnaire

A questionnaire designed for this study was used. The interviews were conducted by trained investigators using a uniform protocol which was set up to minimize error and bias. Baseline demographic information which consisted of sex, age, marital status, education level, location. Information about knowledge, attitudes and practices related to malaria and intestinal coccidian parasites was collected. Information was also collected on travel history of participants.

The questions on knowledge included; if the participants were aware of malaria, the signs and symptoms, its causes, mosquito behaviour such as breeding and resting sites, frequent biting time, its transmission and prevention.

Questions on attitude included health seeking behaviours and on prevention. Questions on practice including practices related to prevention. Similarly, questions on knowledge of coccidian parasites, attitudes and practices related to intestinal coccidian prevention were included.

For the qualitative component of the study, questions included on the awareness of malaria and coccidian parasites, transmissions, treatments and their prevention. In-depth interviews were conducted using a semi-structured interview guide. Using face to face interviews and in the English language, Kom, and Fulfulde, data was collected from participants. After interviewing 9 participants, data saturation was achieved.

Specimen Collection and Processing

Upon signing the consent form to participate in the study, participants were instructed on the procedure to follow to collect their stool samples. Each participant collected a teaspoon full of stool sample into a labelled sterile stool container. In addition about 4 mL of whole blood was collected into an EDTA anti-

coagulated tube to perform to complete blood count (CBC). Thick and thin films were prepared for malaria microscopy. The HIV test was also performed on the blood samples to determine the HIV status for participants who voluntarily accepted to do so.

Parasitological analysis

Detection of malaria parasites were obtained by preparing a thick and thin film on glass slides. Both films were allowed to air dry for approximately 30 minutes. Methanol was used to fix the thin blood films, followed by staining with 10% Giemsa for 45 mins according to established standards (Berzosa et al., 2018) and carefully examined under a microscope by trained laboratory scientists. If parasite was observed, the density was determine using the procedure described (Njunda et al., 2020).

Stool was analysed using the normal saline wet mount and formol-ether concentration techniques as described by Cheersbrough (2006).

Data Analysis

Data collected were entered into Microsoft excel, 2016 (Microsoft Corporation Inc. USA), and transported to the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 26.0 (IBM-SPSS, Inc., Illinois, USA). Descriptive statistics were used to summarise the data in tables. Categorical data, was presented using frequencies, counts, and percentages. Continuous variables such as attitudes were summarized using means and standard deviations. Association between categorical variables were tested using Chi-square (χ^2) and Fisher's exact tests. Comparison of proportions was done using cross-tabulations Pearson product-moment correlations were performed to observe associations between attitudes and practices. Computed mean scores were also compared to the score range on the *Likert-scale* table to make inferences on the overall attitudes of participants. Univariate and multivariate logistic regression models were used to identify predictors of knowledge and practices towards malaria and intestinal coccidian parasite prevention. A *p-value* of 0.05 or less was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Consideration

The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board of the Faculty of health Sciences, University of Buea, Cameroon. Administrative clearance was obtained from the regional delegation of public health for the Northwest Region of Cameroon. All study procedures were conducted according to good clinical practice. All eligible participants were asked to provide their consent by signing an informed consent form before enrolment in this study.

Results

Participants' Knowledge of Malaria, Causes and Modes of Transmission and Prevention and Health Seeking Behaviours

A total of three hundred and sixty-seven (367) adult malaria patients were approached and introduced to the study. Three hundred and thirty-330 (89.9%) were successfully. The mean age (\pm SD) of the participants was 37.02(\pm 15.24) years. There were 215(65%) females and 115 (35%) males. Sixty-four (64), were found co-infected with intestinal coccidian parasites giving a prevalence of 64/330 (19.4%). Malaria co-infection prevalence with other intestinal parasites was 18/330 (5.5%). More than eight

27/330 (8.2%) percent of the participants were diagnosed with HIV. There was overlapping co-infections occurring in some health areas.

Participants main sources of information on malaria were: television (TV) and radio 111/330 (34%), community health workers (CHWs) 109/330 (33%), and Hospitals (37%). A majority 296/330 (90%) knew malaria was transmitted through a mosquito bite. Participants' knowledge of the malaria causative agent was poor 8/330 (2%). The majority 296/330(90%) of the participants had good knowledge of mosquito frequent biting time is during the night time. More than half 229 (69%) knew that mosquito usual resting places are dark corners, 175(53%) indicated dirty areas. About one-fifth 7(20%) knew it was the edges of the river or streams, and Six 20/330(6%) percent knew animal shed as mosquito hiding places. Questioned on ways to prevent the mosquito from multiplying, 281/330(85%), indicated the cleaning of the house surroundings, 180/330(55%) said it by clearing the bushes, and 113/330(34%) responded that it was by draining away all stagnant waters around our dwellings. Eighty-nine 295/330 (89%) of the participants indicated that they knew ITN are used to prevent mosquito bites.

Table 1. Knowledge of Malaria Vector Behaviour, causes, modes of transmission and prevention, and health seeking behaviours, symptoms and associated risk factors (N=330)

Variable	Category	Response	Simple	Severe	Total	%	P-value
Source of information on malaria	TV and Radio	No	40	179	219	66	0.439
		Yes	16	95	111	34	
	CHW	No	38	183	221	67	1
		Yes	18	91	109	33	
	Hospital	No	34	175	209	63	0.651
		Yes	22	99	121	37	
Mode of malaria transmission	Mosquito bites	No	7	27	34	10	0.628
		Yes	49	247	296	90	
Causes of malaria	Plasmodium species	No	42	280	322	98	0.012
		Yes	1	7	8	2	
Mosquito frequent biting time	During night-time	No	9	24	33	10	0.138
		Yes	47	250	297	90	
mosquito resting places	Dark corners	No	29	72	101	31	0.001
		Yes	27	202	229	69	
	Dirty areas	No	30	125	155	47	0.305
		Yes	26	149	175	53	
	Edge of rivers	No	42	221	263	80	0.363
		Yes					

		Yes	14	53	67	20	
	Animal sheds	No	54	256	310	94	0.546
		Yes	2	18	20	6	
Ways to prevent mosquito breeding sites	Cleaning house surrounding	No	16	33	49	15	0.003
		Yes	40	241	281	85	
	Clearing of bushes around the house	No	33	117	150	45	0.028
		Yes	23	157	180	55	
Draining stagnant water	No	38	179	217	66	0.759	
	Yes	18	95	113	34		
Use of Insecticides treated net	ITNs	No	7	28	35	11	0.634
		Yes	49	246	295	89	
What makes you seek for healthcare in a facility	Condition of the illness	No	8	34	42	13	0.664
		Yes	48	240	288	87	
	Cost of treatment	No	52	257	309	94	0.766
		Yes	4	17	21	6	
Where malaria can be best managed	By traditional medicines	No	56	270	326	99	1
		Yes	0	4	4	1	
	Hospital	No	34	175	209	63	0.651
		Yes	22	99	121	37	
	Self-medication	No	50	256	306	93	0.266
		Yes	6	18	25	7	
Symptoms of malaria	Fever Symptom	No	5	39	44	13	0.389
		Yes	51	235	286	87	
	Weakness	No	48	247	295	89	0.342
		Yes	8	27	35	11	
	Vomiting	No	37	195	232	70	
		Yes	19	79	98	30	0.571
	Diarrheal	No	35	168	203	62	1
		Yes	21	106	127	38	

On participants' health seeking behaviours, a majority 288/330 (87%) indicated that they will visit a health facility to consult only depending on the severity of the illness and 21/330 (6%), were concerned about the cost of treatment before visiting a health facility to seek healthcare services. Questioned on where malaria can be best managed, 1% indicated traditional medicines, 121(37%) indicated health facility and (7%) stated self-medication. On the knowledge of clinical symptoms, fever was the most widely known clinical symptom mentioned by participants 286(87%), followed by diarrhoea 127/330 (38%), vomiting 98/330 (30%), and body weakness 35/330(11%).

A statistically significant difference in knowledge score was observed among those who knew the causative agent for malaria was *Plasmodium* species, (P -value=0.011) and among those who knew mosquito resting places for malaria vector were the dark corners (P -value=0.019). There was a statistically significant difference observed

in the knowledge score among those who knew that ways to prevent the mosquito from multiplying in their breeding sites was to a) clean the surroundings of the house b) clear the bushes around human dwelling environments. (P -value=0.003).

Participants Knowledge of Coccidian Intestinal Parasites, Causes and Modes of Transmission and Prevention

More than nineteen 64/330 (19.4%) percent of the participants cautiously knew about opportunistic intestinal parasites (OIPs). Knowledge of OIPs can be found in unsafe drinking water was significantly below average 155/330 (47%) P -value=0.036 (Table 2). A large majority 284(86%) knew that poor hygiene can transmit OIPs in the population. More than two-thirds of the participants 293/330 (89%) knew that washing the hands with clean running water can also prevent the spread of OIPs. The knowledge that swimming pools, can transmit OIPs, was below average 109/330 (32.8%).

Participants also had poor knowledge 103 (31.2%) that animals can transmit coccidian parasites in the population. Knowledge that exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) can prevent OIPs transmission in children and subsequently to adults was poor 87 (26.4%). Knowledge was

significantly low 105 (31.9%) about the population that was most at risk of opportunistic intestinal coccidian infections $\chi^2(df)$ (15.276(5) P -value=0.009.

Table 2. Knowledge of Coccidian Parasites and Environmental Risk Factors in Association with Its Prevalence in Adult Malaria Patients (N=330)

Variables	Simple n (%)	Severe n (%)	Total n (%)	X ²	P-value
Heard of OIPs					
No	43 (76.8)	223 (81.4)	266 (80.6)	0.63	0.427
Yes	13 (23.2)	51 (18.6)	64 (19.4)		
OIPs are found in unsafe water					
No	22 (40)	152 (55.5)	174 (52.9)	4.402	0.036
Yes	33 (60)	122 (44.5)	155 (47.1)		
Poor hygiene can transmit OIPs					
No	5 (9.1)	40 (14.6)	45 (13.7)	1.177	0.278
Yes	50 (90.9)	234 (85.4)	284 (86.3)		
Clean water should be used in hand washing to prevent OIPs					
No	6 (10.7)	30 (11)	36 (10.9)	0.004	0.952
Yes	50 (89.3)	243 (89)	293 (89.1)		
Swimming pools water can also transmit OIPs					
No	35 (62.5)	186 (68.1)	221 (67.2)	0.668	0.414
Yes	21 (37.5)	87 (31.9)	108 (32.8)		
Animals can transmit OIPs					
No	37 (66.1)	190 (69.3)	227 (68.8)	0.232	0.63
Yes	19 (33.9)	84 (30.7)	103 (31.2)		
EBF can prevent transmission of OIPs in children					
No	44 (78.6)	199 (72.6)	243 (73.6)	0.846	0.358
Yes	12 (21.4)	75 (27.4)	87 (26.4)		
People more likely to be infected with OIPs					
Children	12 (21.8)	73 (26.6)	85 (25.8)	15.276	0.009
Young adults	2 (3.6)	19 (6.9)	21 (6.4)		
People with weak immunity	1 (1.8)	15 (5.5)	16 (4.9)		
The elderly	6 (10.9)	63 (22.6)	69 (20.7)		
All the above	22 (40.0)	83 (30.33)	105 (31.9)		
I don't know	12 (21.8)	22 (8.0)	34 (10.3)		

Participants' Socio-Demographic Factors Associated with Knowledge and Practices Towards Malaria and Coccidian Parasite Prevention

Sex and occupation were not associated with knowledge score of participants on environmental risk factors associated with opportunistic intestinal coccidian parasite transmission (Table 3 – Appendix 1). The poor

knowledge of environmental risk factors as transmission routes for intestinal coccidian parasites significantly increased with age. The younger age groups were more knowledgeable than adults. The area of residence, marital status and the level of education were significantly associated with participants knowledge score in the study.

Participants' Attitudes Towards Hygiene and Sanitation Practices Associated with Transmission of Coccidian Parasites

Some appropriate attitudes were demonstrated by participants towards bad hygiene and sanitation practices. These facilitated the transmission of coccidian parasitic infections in

the population. A majority of participants *'agreed'* to the statement 'boiling water before drinking removes diseases causing micro-organisms' [95% CI: 1.78-1.9] with a mean score of 1.84. Similarly, a majority *'neither agree nor disagree'* to the statement that "waste can be a breeding sites for flies and rodents" [95% CI: 2.41-2.62] with a mean score of 2.51, and also a majority of the participants *'disagreed'* to the statement: "Human waste from filled latrines should be emptied into rivers as good practices to get rid of waste from homes". A similar positive attitude was expressed when a majority also *'agreed'* to the statement that "defecating in water can lead to water borne diseases" (Table 4).

Table 4. Mean Score of Attitudes of Participants Towards Hygiene and Sanitation Practices (N=330)

Variables	Mean	SD	95% Confident interval	
			Lower band	Upper band
Boiling water before drinking removes disease causing micro-organisms	1.84	0.524	1.78	1.9
Waste can be breeding site for flies and rodents	2.51	0.968	2.41	2.62
Human waste from filled latrines should be emptied into rivers/runoffs as good practice	3.64	1.047	3.52	3.75
OIPs can be found in flood waters	2.45	1.016	2.34	2.56
Defecating in water can lead to water borne diseases	1.88	0.684	1.81	1.96

Note: OIPs=Opportunistic intestinal parasites.

Participants Practices on Hygiene and Sanitation Towards Malaria and Coccidian Parasitic Prevention and Control

Participants who were found co-infected with both malaria and coccidian intestinal parasites were assessed on a wide range of practices that increases the risk of malaria-intestinal coccidian co-infection (Table 5). Thirty six percent 23/64 (36%) were living in the house with children less than two years old. four percent 60/64 (94%) used the latrine, and sixty four 41/64(64%) percent, had a hand washing facility at home. Fourteen 9/64(14%) percent practiced washing their hands with water running water using soap. Most of the participants lived in homes 50/64(78%) with domestic animals and

1/64(2%), disinfected their animal shed/farms. More than half 41/64(64%) would "some time" disinfect their animals farms. Twenty-two 14/64 (22%) percent fetched their drinking water from unprotected sources. Only 4/64(6.3%) practice treating water by boiling before drinking, and 3/64(4.7%) drink chlorinated water. Ninety-two 59/64(92%) of participants owned at least a mosquito bed net with only 22/64 (34%) as household members sleeping under a mosquito bed net. Twenty-three percent 15/64(23%) of the participants knew that practicing EBF prevents coccidian parasite infections in children and subsequently transmission to adults. Materials used for hand washing, source of drinking water and the use of insecticide treated net (ITN), significantly influenced prevalent

scores on practices to prevent malaria and coccidian infections, P -value <0.05 at the 95%

confident interval (Table 6) P -value=0.052, P -value=0.051, P -value=0.019).

Table 5. Environmental characteristics associated with coccidian parasitic infection (N=64)

Variable	Coccidian parasite			n	%	χ^2	df	P .value
	A	B	C					
Child in household less than 2 years								
No	27	4	10	41	64	2.061	2	0.357
Yes	19	1	3	23	36			
Do all members of household use latrine								
No	3	1	0	4	6	2.486	2	0.289
Yes	43	4	13	60	94			
Household latrine have hand washing facility/Running tap/bowl								
No	16	2	5	23	36	.098	2	0.952
Yes	30	3	8	41	64			
Materials used for hand washing								
Water and soap/ash	3	1	5	9	14	8.957	4	0.052
Water only	42	4	8	54	84			
N/A	1	0	0	1	2			
Keeping domestic animals/pets								
No	10	0	4	14	28	2.002	2	0.367
Yes	36	5	9	50	78			
Do you disinfect animal shed?								
All the time	1	0	0	1	2	1.102	6	0.981
Sometimes	30	3	8	41	64			
Not at all	14	2	5	21	33			
N/A	1	0	0	1	2			
Source of drinking water?								
Protected pump/spring	38	2	10	50	78	4.805	2	0.051
Unprotected river/spring	8	3	3	14	22			
Treat water before drinking?								
No	43	3	11	57	92	3.282	2	0.194
Yes	2	1	2	5	8			
Water treatment method?								
Boil	2	1	1	4	6.3	8.507	8	0.386
Add chlorine	3	0	0	3	4.7			
Solar	4	0	0	4	6.3			
Let it stand and settle	37	4	11	52	52			
None of the above	0	0	1	1	1			
ITNs								
No	2	2	1	5	8	7.959	2	0.019
Yes	44	3	12	59	92			
Those currently sleeping under bed-net?								
Children and mothers	31	2	6	39	61	3.617	4	0.460
Everyone in the house	13	3	6	22	34			
No one	2	0	1	3	5			
EBF prevents transmission of OIPs in children and from children to adults								
No	35	5	9	49	77	2.647	4	0.619
Yes	11	0	4	15	23			

Note: EBF=Exclusive breastfeeding, OIP=Opportunistic intestinal parasites, ITNs=Insecticides treated nets $a=Cryptosporidium hominis$ $b=Isospora belli$, $c=Cyclospora Cayetanensis$

Association Between Knowledge and Attitudes and Between Attitudes and Practices Towards Prevention of Malaria and Coccidian Parasites

The link between knowledge and attitudes and between attitudes and practices scores were assessed. Significant associations were observed influencing knowledge and attitudes scores and between attitude and practices scores. The knowledge of the OIPs found in unsafe water was significantly associated with source of drinking water score $P = 0.001$. Increase in knowledge of OIPs can be found in unsafe water by participants was associated with increased use of water from protected drinking sources with an odds ratio of 3.8 (95% C.I: 2.2-6.6). Increase in knowledge of swimming pools can be a source of infection for intestinal coccidian parasites was associated with increase in the use of protected water sources for drinking with an odds of 2.0 (95% C.I: 1.2-3.3). An increase in the knowledge that OIPs found in unsafe water was associated with a decrease use of hand washing facilities in the households with an odds of 0.3 (95% C.I: 0.2- 0.5) Similarly, an increase in the knowledge of swimming pools being the source of coccidian parasites was associated with a decreases use of hand washing facilities in the households with an odds ratio of 0.3 (95% C.I: 0.2-0.5).

Discussion

This study was undertaken to provide information on the prevalence of pathogenic gastro-intestinal parasites in adult malaria patients, and to assess their knowledge attitudes and practices towards malaria and coccidian parasite prevention and control. We therefore incorporated the knowledge, attitude and practice survey which is recommended by the World Health Organisation as an important tool for health promotional campaigns. Surveys are very important in programme implementation as it helps planners adjust their educational messages aimed to improved public knowledge and attitudes towards any public health concern. Where there is insufficient knowledge and

negative attitudes prevailed, bad practices are bound to significantly contribute to high prevalence of diseases (Hassen Amer, Ashankyty, & Haouas, 2016). In our study we found varied knowledge scores of malaria and coccidian parasite among study participants. Poor practices as well as better practices were observed. Participants portrayed positive attitudes towards environmental hygiene and sanitation. Causes of malaria, mosquito resting places, and ways to prevent mosquito breeding sites, coccidian parasites can be found in unsafe water, people more susceptible to coccidian infection significantly predict the knowledge score. Materials used for hand washing, source of drinking water, and ITN usage significantly predict the practice scores. Significant correlation were also observed between knowledge-attitudes and between attitudes and practices. A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient revealed significant correlations between attitudes and practice scores $r=0.210$, $P\text{-value}=0.001$, $r=0.174$, $P\text{-value}=0.002$., $r=0.203$ $P\text{-value}=0.001$, and between knowledge and attitude scores ($r= -0.177$, $P\text{-value}=0.001$, $r= -0.133$, $P\text{-value}=0.015$).

Knowledge of Malaria Parasite

From our study, a majority of participants had a good knowledge (90%) that malaria was transmitted through a mosquito bite. However, Participants expressed very poor knowledge of the malaria causative agent (2%). Higher rates of causative agent for malaria have been obtained elsewhere in Kojom and Lehman (2018) where 14.3% was obtained and in another study Mbohoun Nchetnkou, Kojom Foko, and Lehman (2020), a rate of 9.4% was also reported in Tanzania (Mazigo et al., 2010) 6% was reported. The Tanzania study and our study have similar tendency of lower rates, due to the study setting (rural) often associated with lower levels of education when compared to urban settings. In addition, it could be an indication that in health sensitization campaigns the causative agent is usually not mentioned. It could be that many of

the participants were confused between causative agent and malaria vector.

Knowledge of other dark corners (69%), and dirty areas (53%) as mosquitoes hiding places was good (above average). However, participants expressed poor knowledge of the edges of rivers (20%) and animal sheds (6%) as resting places for mosquitoes. Higher good knowledge scores were obtained in Douala, Cameroon (Hassen Amer, Ashankyty, & Haouas, 2016), where participants were as high as 90% of participants were very knowledgeable on how malaria could be prevented (90%). Much higher knowledge scores were obtained among participants in the Malaysian study where 85.9%, 81% and 79.9% of the study participants were respectively knowledgeable that draining stagnant water, keeping a clean environment and use of mosquito nets prevent malaria infection respectively (Kader Maideen et al., 2022).

Knowledge of Coccidian Parasites

Our study disclosed that knowledge of opportunistic intestinal coccidian parasites was poor 19.4%. Our finding of 19.4% knowledge of opportunistic intestinal coccidian parasites, was very poor when compared with the 33.5% participant awareness of parasitic food borne diseases young adults in China (Ming & Huan, 2018) and the 40.5% participant poor knowledge of intestinal parasites reported in Yemen (Alharazi et al., 2020). These differences maybe as a result in study designs and settings.

Knowledge levels were also low in our study, as 31.2% knew animals as intermediate hosts for the transmission of intestinal parasites including coccidian parasites. This was similar to a study in rural Iran where knowledge was also low as more than half of the participants were unaware of the existence of zoonotic parasites (Sazmand et al., 2020). The trend clearly demonstrated a generalised low to high knowledge of pathogenic intestinal parasites including coccidian parasites as one moves from rural community setting to urban settings within countries in the tropics and at sub-continental levels. In this study Knowledge scores significantly associated with attitudes scores which in turn associated with participants' practices. The opportunistic

intestinal coccidian parasites are causing emerging diseases associated with zoonotic transmission, human-to-human transmission, food borne and contaminated water. The diseases are among the most neglected tropical diseases (NTDs). In our current study 36% of the participants lived with children less than two years at home, a low proportion (26.4%) of the participants knew EBF can limit the transmission OIPs in children and hence to adults. In Yaoundé, Cameroon a low rate of EBF (38%) has been reported (Ndum Okwen et al., 2022). Generally, the rate of EBF in Cameroon is below average (Ndum Okwen et al., 2022) and evidence showed that higher rates of EBF are being associated with low infant mortality and morbidity (Division of Nutrition, Physical Activity and Obesity, 2020; Tombang et al., 2019). In Kenya a low rate of 39.4% among adult women (Mohamed, Ochola, & Owino, 2018). Thus, improving child care and nutrition would limit the transmission of intestinal parasites hence intestinal coccidian transmission in children and from children to adult.

Attitudes Toward Malaria and Coccidian Parasites

In general, positive attitudes toward good hygiene and sanitation practices aimed at reducing malaria and transmission of intestinal parasitic diseases were expressed in this study. In Ghana, 91% of the respondents showed positive attitudes towards good hygiene practices especially hand washing practices (Omari et al., 2022). With good level of knowledge and attitudes participants are more likely to have good practices to avoid those contracting infectious diseases including intestinal parasitic diseases. Prior knowledge and exposure probably had an influence on the positive attitudes expressed. The knowledge, attitude, and practice theories suggest that the acquisition of health-related knowledge, eventually enhance one's attitudes and leads to good behaviour formation that will ultimately lead to the prevention of diseases (Mazigo et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2020). Our current study found a significant association between education and previous knowledge on coccidian parasites. Studies in Cameroon, Nigeria, Ethiopia

and Zambia, had similar conclusions in which knowledge was significantly associated with the level of education and had a significant impact on diseases prevention practices (Muhammad, Oyewole, & Dipeou, 2021; Taremwa et al., 2017; Oguntade et al., 2018; Jumbam, Stevenson, & Matoba, 2020). Those who received formal education would have been sensitized empowered with knowledge regarding common diseases, their modes of transmission and prevention. A study by Njunda et al. (2016) in Cameroon indicated that higher educational levels were associated with better attitudes. The study concludes that participants who were previously infected with malaria were more aware of the way to prevent it than those who had been exposed but had not been infected. This conclusion was also echoed by Kader et al (2022) in a similar study carried out in Malaysia. We also found gender, age, marital status, and education to be significantly associated with knowledge scores and a correlation between education levels and knowledge score. These findings are similar to those of (Muhammad, Oyewole, & Dipeou, 2021; Taremwa et al., 2017). Both studies concluded that those with good knowledge associated with higher education levels have better practices in the prevention of diseases including malaria.

During interviews positive attitudes toward diseases prevention including malaria and coccidian prevention was expressed.

“Using a mosquito bed net, and keeping a clean environment by clearing bushes around and maintaining good drainage are good practices to prevent mosquito bites and malaria. The issue here is that if I do keep my surroundings clean, my neighbours wouldn’t do the same and the very mosquito would breed around my neighbour’s house and still get me bitten.”

Practices Towards Prevention of Malaria and Coccidian Parasites

In our study we compared the how attitudes influence participants’ practices to prevent and control malaria and intestinal coccidian parasitic infections. Eight malaria preventive methods currently used for malaria prevention were reported in varying proportions. The most

reported good practices enlisted in decreasing order were: ITNs usage was (89%), cutting bushes to clean the environment (34.5%), and the least was closing windows early before dark (1.5%). In Douala, Cameroon a study (Mbohounchetnkou, Kojom Foko, & Lehman, 2020) showed similarly eight preventive measures for malaria were reported by respondents where the most reported preventive practice was ITNs, and in contrast the least reported practice was keeping good hygiene and sanitation. This is also contrary to a study in Malaysia whereby the most reported good practices to prevent malaria among rural indigenous people was removing stagnant water (92.3%), and the least reported was larvicide use in stagnant water where 82% non-usage (Mbohounchetnkou, Kojom Foko, & Lehman, 2020). The use of ITN is the most effective and widely used malaria preventive methods. However, combine application of other preventive measures are essential in preventing mosquito multiplication and resting places. This reduces the number of adult mosquitoes in the environment which are capable of transmitting malaria in the population. Elsewhere in Cameroon lower rates of ITN usage have been reported; with (78.9%) in Yaoundé, 77.23% in Douala and 57.4% in Buea (Mbohounchetnkou, Kojom Foko, & Lehman, 2020; Njunda et al., 2016; Mekachie Sandie et al., 2021).

Over the last five years, the Government of Cameroon supported by its partners have stepped up the distribution of ITNs in all Health Districts across the country. This explains the variations observed in the study with the highest prevalence of ITN usage in our current study. Despite the nation-wide sensitization campaigns, a disparity between ITN possession and usage seems to be wide thus negatively affecting the performance in different settings in Cameroon (Mbohounchetnkou, Kojom Foko, & Lehman, 2020). Improving hygiene and sanitation will ultimately lead to a reduction in the mosquito permanent breeding sites. It will also create an environment where intestinal coccidian parasites cannot thrive. Good environmental hygiene remains a key control strategy for the control and elimination of both

malaria and coccidian parasitic diseases. The use of ITN, was also significantly associated with malaria infection (P -value=0.05). Practices to prevent intestinal coccidian parasitic transmission were assessed. A very low proportion of the participants (9%), practiced washing hands with water and soap. This was lower than the rate reported in Colombia where a much higher proportion of 96% (Contreras-Puentes, Duarte-Amador, & Aparicio-Marengo, 2019).

1. In our current study 4.8% of the participants domesticated animals such as chickens, pigs, goats, sheep, and cattle. Domestic animals in the region and elsewhere in the country have been documented to be an important intermediate host in the life cycles of intestinal parasites (Eshetu et al., 2001; Nfi, 1991) with high potential to cause infections in the human population. This reaffirms the zoonotic potentials of intestinal coccidian parasites to cause pathological conditions in humans if poorly prepared meat is eaten.

Qualitatively, we obtained similar trends during interviews in the community.

"I keep domestic animal such as pigs but since the beginning of the armed conflict in this region, I do not longer vaccinate them because people have been displaced including staff in the veterinary department that I used to contact for vaccines for my animals".

2. Our study revealed that 9% of the participants boil water before drinking, 5% drink chlorinated water, 6% expose their water to solar energy as a means of disinfecting drinking water and a much high proportion (52%) allowed water to settle before drinking. Another study in Cameroon associated water treatment in households to the socio-economic status whereby those with low levels of education, and poverty were less likely to treat their water before drinking. Studies have demonstrated that boiling water before drinking remains the only way to get rid of intestinal coccidian parasites such as *Cryptosporidium hominis* in drinking water (Ssemugabo, et al., 2019; Escobedo, et al., 2009).

The practice of treating water before drinking has been low particularly in rural community settings. Even though considerable efforts have been made to improve water quality in Cameroon, rural community settings have largely been ignored. Our study showed health sensitisation campaigns in Cameroon have largely ignored water treatment as an important issue to educate the population on disease prevention and control. A lack of information on health and ignorance is a contributory factor to poor knowledge and poor practices expose participants in the study to the risk of malaria and intestinal coccidian infections. Intestinal coccidian diseases are new and emerging to the public requiring that public sensitization about the existence, and the threat to public health. More so outbreaks related to these parasites are unknown to the public.

Similar findings were elicited during the interviews regarding outbreaks and treatment.

"We usually witness high diarrhoeal cases between January and April each year. This period coincides with acute water shortage in my health area. People turn to fetch drinking from all sort of places you can never imagine (River, stream). Our community water taps usually run dry and our health centre relies on the borehole. Sometimes community members approach us to beg us for water from the well to drink"

Another had this to say.

"We have never bothered in making request for medications that are specific to treating coccidian infection because we do not have adequate knowledge on the disease nor the clinical manifestations. We however always have medications to treat malaria".

Participants' Health Seeking Behaviours

In this study we compared participant's knowledge, attitudes and practices to understand their influence on health seeking behaviours. Eighty-seven (87 %) percent of the participants visited a health facility for medical attention depending on the severity of the disease condition. Six (6%) percent were worried about the cost of treatment, one (1%) percent preferred a tradition healer, thirty (37%) seven

percent would use the hospital, while seven (7%) percent carried out self-medication. Nounouce et al. (2009), obtained a higher prevalence rate of 1.4% where participants acknowledge that malaria can be best managed by traditional healers. Elsewhere in Cameroon similar trends have been observed (Kappagoda, Singh, & Blackburn, 2011). From the study we could observe that it's the nature of the illness that was a key determinant that would influence the patients' health seeking behavioural pattern.

Our study also revealed that age, group, gender, marital status and occupation were key determinants of observed knowledge which influenced practices that were observed. This is contrary to (Nounouce et al., 2022) where the level of education was a key determinant factor of a household health seeking behaviour. A study in Turkey by Abudu et al. (2022) reported that participants were instead worried about the cost of treatment as a key factor to have influence patients seeking healthcare. We observed that 6% of the patient co-infected with intestinal coccidian diseases had simple malaria compared to 94% with severe malaria. Delay between onset of malaria and coccidian diseases and seeking healthcare is sufficient to increase the seriousness of the illness and death since malaria has the capacity to kill within hours of onset of symptoms (Nounouce et al., 2022).

Similar findings were obtained during the interviews regarding health seeking behaviours.

"We received patients in this health facility mostly when the health condition is already deteriorating. When they start to experience symptoms of malaria, the first thing they do is buy medications from nearby vendors or visit a traditional healer. Its only when they find out that their health condition is not improving that they rush to meet us".

In this current study, a low proportion (16.4%) of participants reported hand washing using soap, while 36% were living with children less than two years. Elsewhere in Cameroon, prevalence of hand washing with soap at 10.7% (Yakum et al., 2017) has been reported. A study in Ethiopia (Abuduxike et al., 2020) revealed good compliance to hand hygiene significantly

reduce the risk of intestinal infection by 52%. Children have been associated with poor hygiene practices and their risk of intestinal diseases including coccidian infection is high (Mbouthieu Teumta et al., 2019). The risk of the human-to-human transmission of the coccidian parasite from children to the adult is also heightened.

Conclusion

Knowledge of malaria and intestinal coccidian co-infection was below average among participants. Misconceptions and bad behaviours were observed that exposed the population to high risk of malaria and intestinal infections. Gender, marital status, education and age were significantly associated with knowledge, attitude and practice scores.

Health education should emphasise on the causes of malaria and educating the public on intestinal coccidian parasites diseases including associated environmental risk factors. Primary healthcare services are an important entry point to make any meaningful change.

Abbreviations

χ^2 ; Chi square, 95% C.I; 95% Confidence Interval, df; Degree of freedom, EBF; Exclusive Breastfeeding, ITN; Insecticide Treated Nets, NTDs; Neglected Tropical Diseases, OIPs; Opportunistic Intestinal Parasites, WHO; World Health Organisation.

Competing Interests

The authors declared that they have no competing interests.

Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate

The study protocol was approved by the Faculty of Health Sciences Institutional Review Board (FHS IRB). Administrative authorization was gotten from the Regional Delegation of Public Health for the North West Region, the District

Medical Officer (DMO) for Fundong Health District and Chiefs of Centre for the various health facilities where data was collected.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all the staff of the 16 health units for facilitating the field work throughout the study period. Our appreciation also goes to the administration of the Catholic General Hospital Njinikom for letting me use their laboratory services. Our appreciation goes to Mr Teh Emmanuel, Young Augustine, for laboratory analysis of blood and all stool samples and all community members that participated in the study.

Authors Contributions

ANL conceived designed and coordinated the study. JFA, participated in the design of the study, review statistical analysis and revised the paper, BPT, participated in the design of the study, review statistical analysis and revised the paper, FPA participated in data collection, took part in the analysis and interpretations, and conducted the literature search and review and wrote the final draft of the paper. All authors read and approved the final paper.

Data Availability Statement

All relevant data that supports the conclusion of this study are included in the article.

References

Abuduxike, G., Aşut, Ö., Vaizoglu, S. A., & Cali, S. (2020). Health-Seeking Behaviors and its Determinants: A Facility-Based Cross-Sectional Study in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. *International journal of health policy and management*, 9(6), 240–249. <https://doi.org/10.15171/ijhpm.2019.106>

Alharazi, T., Bamaga, O. A., Al-Abd, N., & Alcantara, J. C. (2020). Intestinal parasitic infection: prevalence, knowledge, attitude, and

practices among schoolchildren in an urban area of Taiz city, Yemen. *AIMS public health*, 7(4), 769–777.

<https://doi.org/10.3934/publichealth.2020059>

Antonio-Nkondjio, C., Ndo, C., Njiokou, F., Bigoga, J. D., Awono-Ambene, P., Etang, J., Ekobo, A. S., & Wondji, C. S. (2019). Review of malaria situation in Cameroon: technical viewpoint on challenges and prospects for disease elimination. *Parasites & vectors*, 12(1), 501. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-019-3753-8>

Assob, J. C., Nde, P. F., Nsagha, D. S., Njimoh, D. L., Nfor, O., Njunda, A. L., & Kamga, H. L. (2012). The incidence of feco-oral parasites in street-food vendors in Buea, south-west region Cameroon. *African health sciences*, 12(3), 376–380. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v12i3.20>

Berzosa, P., de Lucio, A., Romay-Barja, M., Herrador, Z., González, V., García, L., Fernández-Martínez, A., Santana-Morales, M., Ncogo, P., Valladares, B., Riloha, M., & Benito, A. (2018). Comparison of three diagnostic methods (microscopy, RDT, and PCR) for the detection of malaria parasites in representative samples from Equatorial Guinea. *Malaria journal*, 17(1), 333. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-018-2481-4>

CDC. (2021). Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report. Malaria Surveillance — United States, 2017. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/volumes/70/ss/pdfs/ss7002a1-H.pdf>

Cheesbrough, M. (2006). *District Laboratory Practice in Tropical Countries*. Second ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Contreras-Puentes, N., Duarte-Amador, D., & Aparicio-Marenco, D. (2019). *Intestinal Coccidian: An overview epidemiology worldwide and Colombia*. University Corporation Rafael Nunez, Faculty of Sciences of Health, Medicine, Colombia.

Division of Nutrition, Physical Activity and Obesity (2020). *Breastfeeding Report Card*. United States. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/breastfeeding/pdf/2020-breastfeeding-report-card-h.pdf>

- Escobedo, A. A., Almirall, P., Alfonso, M., Cimerman, S., Rey, S., & Terry, S. L. (2009). Treatment of intestinal protozoan infections in children. *Archives of disease in childhood*, 94(6), 478–482. <https://doi.org/10.1136/adc.2008.151852>
- Eshetu, Y., Mulualem, E., Ibrahim, H., Berhanu, A., & Aberra, K. (2001). Study of gastrointestinal helminths of scavenging chickens in four rural districts of Amhara region, Ethiopia. *Revue scientifique et technique (International Office of Epizootics)*, 20(3), 791–796. <https://doi.org/10.20506/rst.20.3.1310>
- Harhay, M. O., Horton, J., & Olliaro, P. L. (2010). Epidemiology and control of human gastrointestinal parasites in children. *Expert review of anti-infective therapy*, 8(2), 219–234. <https://doi.org/10.1586/eri.09.119>
- Hassen Amer, O., Ashankyty, I. M., & Haouas, N. A. (2016). Prevalence of intestinal parasite infections among patients in local public hospitals of Hail, Northwestern Saudi Arabia. *Asian Pacific journal of tropical medicine*, 9(1), 44–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apjtm.2015.12.009>
- Jumbam, D.T., Stevenson, J.C., & Matoba, J. (2020). Knowledge, attitudes and practices assessment of malaria interventions in rural Zambia. *BMC Public Health*, 20, 216. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-8235-6>
- Kader Maideen, S. F., Rashid, A., Ahmad, N. I., Zahari, S. N. A., & Hamat, R. A. (2022). Seroprevalence of malaria and the knowledge, attitudes and practices relating to the prevention of malaria among indigenous people living in the central forest spine in Peninsular Malaysia: a mixed-methods study. *Malaria journal*, 21(1), 281. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-022-04293-5>
- Kamga, H. L., Shey, D. N., Assob, J. C., Njunda, A. L., Nde Fon, P., & Njem, P. K. (2011). Prevalence of onchocerciasis in the Fundong Health District, Cameroon after 6 years of continuous community-directed treatment with ivermectin. *The Pan African medical journal*, 10, 34.
- Kappagoda, S., Singh, U., & Blackburn, B. G. (2011). Antiparasitic therapy. *Mayo Clinic proceedings*, 86(6), 561–583. <https://doi.org/10.4065/mcp.2011.0203>
- Kojom, L.P. & Lehman, L. (2018). Knowledge and Beliefs towards Malaria and Associated Factors among Residents of the Town of Douala, Cameroon. *Archives of Environmental Health an International Journal*, 14, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ACRI/2018/43009>
- Liu, L., Liu, Y. P., Wang, J., An, L. W., & Jiao, J. M. (2016). Use of a knowledge-attitude-behaviour education programme for Chinese adults undergoing maintenance haemodialysis: Randomized controlled trial. *The Journal of international medical research*, 44(3), 557–568. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0300060515604980>
- Mazigo, H. D., Obasy, E., Mauka, W., Manyiri, P., Zinga, M., Kweka, E. J., Mnyone, L. L., & Heukelbach, J. (2010). Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices about Malaria and Its Control in Rural Northwest Tanzania. *Malaria research and treatment*, 2010, 794261. <https://doi.org/10.4061/2010/794261>
- Mbohoun Nchetnkou, C., Kojom Foko, L. P., & Lehman, L. G. (2020). Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices towards Malaria among Employees from Enterprises in the Town of Douala, Cameroon. *BioMed research international*, 2020, 8652084. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8652084>
- Mbohoun Nchetnkou, C., Kojom Foko, L. P., & Lehman, L. G. (2020). Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices towards Malaria among Employees from Enterprises in the Town of Douala, Cameroon. *BioMed research international*, 2020, 8652084. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8652084>
- Mbouthieu Teumta, G. M., Niba, L. L., Ncheuveu, N. T., Ghumbemsitia, M. T., Itor, P. O. B., Chongwain, P., & Navti, L. K. (2019). An Institution-Based Assessment of Students' Hand Washing Behavior. *BioMed research international*, 2019, 7178645. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/7178645>
- Mekachie Sandie, S., Sumbele, I. U. N., Tasah, M. M., & Kimbi, H. K. (2021). Malaria and intestinal parasite co-infection and its association with anaemia among people living with HIV in Buea, Southwest Cameroon: A community-based retrospective cohort study. *PloS one*, 16(1),

e0245743.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0245743>

Ming, Z., & Huan, L. (2018). *Zhongguo xue xi chong bing fang zhi za zhi = Chinese journal of schistosomiasis control*, 30(3), 349–352. <https://doi.org/10.16250/j.32.1374.2017124>

MOH. (2018). Demographic and Health Survey. Summary Report. Retrieved from <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/SR266/SR266.pdf>

Mohamed, M. J., Ochola, S., & Owino, V. O. (2018). Comparison of knowledge, attitudes and practices on exclusive breastfeeding between primiparous and multiparous mothers attending Wajir District hospital, Wajir County, Kenya: a cross-sectional analytical study. *International breastfeeding journal*, 13, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13006-018-0151-3>

Muhammad, H., Oyewole, O.E., & Dipeou, I.O. (2021). Knowledge and perception of malaria among Hausa married men in Mokola Community of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Environment and Public Health*, 5(2), em0085. <https://doi.org/10.21601/ejeph/11095>

National Institute of Statistic, Cameroon. (2022). Key results from the 2022 Cameroon Malaria Indicator Survey. Retrieved from <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/PR145/PR145.pdf>

Ndum Okwen, G. A., Karimuribo, E. D., Ngowi, H. A., & Fombang, E. N. (2022). Exclusive Breastfeeding and Its Determinants in Yaoundé, Cameroon: A Retrospective Survival Analysis. *Journal of pregnancy*, 2022, 8396586. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8396586>

Nfi N. A. (1991). Soremouth in sheep and goats at the Mankon Animal Research Station, Cameroon. *Revue d'elevage et de medecine veterinaire des pays tropicaux*, 44(2), 141–142.

Njunda, A. L., Fon, S. G., Assob, J. C., Nsagha, D. S., Kwenti, T. D., & Kwenti, T. E. (2015). Coinfection with malaria and intestinal parasites, and its association with anaemia in children in Cameroon. *Infectious diseases of poverty*, 4, 43. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40249-015-0078-5>

Njunda, A. L., Njumkeng, C., Nsagha, S. D., Assob, J. C., & Kwenti, T. E. (2016). The prevalence of malaria in people living with HIV in Yaounde, Cameroon. *BMC public health*, 16, 964. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-3647-z>

Nounouce, N. P. J., Zakariaou, N., Yollande, T., Marie-José, E., Wilfred, M. F., & Roger, S. M. (2022). Determinants of health seeking behaviours for malaria treatment in Cameroon. *International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health*, 9(11), 3980–3989. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-023-04509-2>

Nsagha, D. S., Njunda, A. L., Assob, N. J. C., Ayima, C. W., Tanue, E. A., Kibu, O. D., & Kwenti, T. E. (2016). Intestinal parasitic infections in relation to CD4(+) T cell counts and diarrhea in HIV/AIDS patients with or without antiretroviral therapy in Cameroon. *BMC infectious diseases*, 16, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-016-1337-1>

Nsoh, F. A., Wung, B. A., Atashili, J., Benjamin, P. T., Marvlyn, E., Ivo, K. K., & Nguedia, A. J. (2016). Prevalence, characteristics and correlates of enteric pathogenic protozoa in drinking water sources in Molyko and Bomaka, Cameroon: a cross-sectional study. *BMC microbiology*, 16(1), 268. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-016-0890-5>

Oguntade, E.S., Shohaimi, S.N.M. & Lamidi-Sarumoh, A.A. (2018). Factors influencing malaria knowledge, attitude and practice in Gwagwalada. *International Journal of Science and Healthcare Research*, 3(3), 168 - 178.

Omari, R., Zotor, F., Baah-Tuahene, S., & Arthur, W. (2022). Handwashing knowledge, attitudes, and practices in Ghana. *Journal of preventive medicine and hygiene*, 63(1), E59–E68. <https://doi.org/10.15167/2421-4248/jpmh2022.63.1.2271>

Same-Ekobe, A. (1997). *Santé, climat et environnement au Cameroun*. Yaoundé, Jutey-Sciences, Cameroon.

Sazmand, A., Alipoor, G., Zafari, S., Zolhavarieh, S. M., Alanazi, A. D., & Sargison, N. D. (2020). Assessment of Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices Relating to Parasitic

Diseases and Anthelmintic Resistance Among Livestock Farmers in Hamedan, Iran. *Frontiers in veterinary science*, 7, 584323. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.584323>

Ssemugabo, C., Wafula, S. T., Ndejjo, R., Oporia, F., Osuret, J., Musoke, D., & Halage, A. A. (2019). Knowledge and practices of households on safe water chain maintenance in a slum community in Kampala City, Uganda. *Environmental health and preventive medicine*, 24(1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12199-019-0799-3>

Standley, C. J., Graeden, E., Kerr, J., Sorrell, E. M., & Katz, R. (2018). Decision support for evidence-based integration of disease control: A proof of concept for malaria and schistosomiasis. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*, 12(4), e0006328. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0006328>

Taremwa, I. M., Ashaba, S., Adrama, H. O., Ayebazibwe, C., Omoding, D., Kemeza, I., Yatuha, J., Turuho, T., MacDonald, N. E., & Hilliard, R. (2017). Knowledge, attitude and behaviour towards the use of insecticide treated mosquito nets among pregnant women and children in rural Southwestern Uganda. *BMC public health*, 17(1), 794. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-017-4824-4>

Tombang, A. N., Ambe, N. F., Bobga, T. P., Nkfusai, C. N., Collins, N. M., Ngwa, S. B., Diengou, N. H., & Cumber, S. N. (2019). Prevalence and risk factors associated with cryptosporidiosis among children within the ages 0-5 years attending the Limbe regional hospital, southwest region, Cameroon. *BMC public health*, 19(1), 1144. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-7484-8>

Vouking, M. Z., Enoke, P., Tamo, C. V., & Tadenfok, C. N. (2014). Prevalence of intestinal parasites among HIV patients at the Yaoundé Central Hospital, Cameroon. *The Pan African medical journal*, 18, 136. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2014.18.136.3052>

Wang, J., Chen, L., Yu, M., & He, J. (2020). Impact of knowledge, attitude, and practice

(KAP)-based rehabilitation education on the KAP of patients with intervertebral disc herniation. *Annals of palliative medicine*, 9(2), 388–393. <https://doi.org/10.21037/apm.2020.03.01>

Warren C. A. (2009). Cyclosporiasis: an update. *Current infectious disease reports*, 11(2), 108–112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11908-009-0016-4>

WHO. (2022) Malaria fact sheet. Geneva: WHO. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/malaria>

World Bank. (2019). Lifting Cameroons most vulnerable out of poverty building resilience and fostering local governance to address the root causes of fragility and conflict in northern regions of Cameroon. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/results/2019/11/08/lifting-cameroons-most-vulnerable-out-of-poverty-building-resilience-and-fostering-local-governance-to-address-the-root-causes-of-fragility-and-conflict-in-northern-regions-of-cameroon>

World Health Organization. (2022). World Malaria Report 2022. Geneva. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/teams/global-malaria-programme/reports/world-malaria-report-2022>

Yakum, M. N., Ateudjieu, J., Guenou, E., Walter, E. A., Ram, M., Debes, A. K., Njimbina, A. C., Nafack, S. S., & Sack, D. A. (2017). Health seeking behaviour among suspected cases of cholera in Cameroonian health districts in Lake Chad basin. *BMC research notes*, 10(1), 433. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-017-2756-9>

Zvinorova, P. I., Halimani, T. E., Muchadeyi, F. C., Matika, O., Riggio, V., & Dzama, K. (2016). Prevalence and risk factors of gastrointestinal parasitic infections in goats in low-input low-output farming systems in Zimbabwe. *Small ruminant research : the journal of the International Goat Association*, 143, 75–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smallrumres.2016.09.005>

Appendix 1

Table 3. Socio-Demographic Factors Associated with Knowledge and Practices Scores Towards Malaria and Coccidian Parasite Prevention

Variables	Swimming pools water can also transmit OIPs				Animals can transmit OIPs			EBF can prevent transmission of OIPs in children				
	No	Yes	X ²	P-value	No	Yes	X ²	P-value	No	Yes	X ²	P-value
Sex												
Male	85 (38.5)	30 (27.8)	3.642	0.056	84 (37.0)	31 (30.1)	1.489	0.222	90 (37.0)	25 (28.7)	1.944	0.163
Female	136 (61.5)	78 (72.2)			143 (63.0)	72 (69.9)			153 (63.0)	62 (71.3)		
Age Group												
< 25	67 (30.3)	35 (32.4)	17.048	0.004	68 (30.0)	35 (34.0)	18.352	0.003	73 (30.0)	30 (34.5)	9.278	0.098
26 - 35	48 (21.7)	40 (37.0)			50 (22.0)	38 (36.9)			59 (24.3)	29 (33.3)		
36 - 45	40 (18.1)	19 (17.6)			41 (18.1)	18 (17.5)			45 (18.5)	14 (16.1)		
46 - 55	26 (11.8)	9 (8.3)			30 (13.2)	5 (4.9)			26 (10.7)	9 (10.3)		
56 - 65	27 (12.2)	4 (3.7)			24 (10.6)	7 (6.8)			26 (10.7)	5 (5.7)		
≥ 66	13 (5.9)	1 (0.9)			14 (6.2)	0 (0)			14 (5.8)	0 (0)		
Occupation												
Skilled	49 (22.4)	23 (21.5)	0.032	0.857	51 (22.7)	21 (20.6)	0.177	0.674	51 (21.1)	21 (24.7)	0.483	0.487
Unskilled	170 (77.6)	84 (78.5)			174 (77.3)	81 (79.4)			191 (78.9)	64 (75.3)		
Health Area												
Abuh	4 (1.8)	1 (0.9)	55.052	0.000	5 (2.2)	0 (0)	67.168	0.000	5 (2.1)	0 (0)	28.265	0.005
Aduk	2 (0.9)	0 (0)			2 (0.9)	0 (0)			2 (0.8)	0 (0)		
Anjin	3 (1.4)	2 (1.9)			3 (1.3)	2 (1.9)			5 (2.1)	0 (0)		
Anyajua	38 (17.2)	13 (12.0)			38 (16.7)	13 (12.6)			35 (14.4)	16 (18.4)		
Belo	33 (14.9)	11 (10.2)			31 (13.7)	13 (12.6)			28 (11.5)	16 (18.4)		
Dichami	1 (0.5)	1 (0.9)			1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)			2 (0.8)	0 (0)		
Fuanantui	51 (23.1)	30 (27.8)			51 (22.5)	30 (29.1)			55 (22.6)	26 (29.9)		
Fundong rural	22 (10.0)	2 (1.9)			22 (9.7)	2 (1.9)			21 (8.6)	3 (3.4)		
Fundong urban	15 (6.8)	4 (3.7)			19 (8.4)	0 (0)			18 (7.4)	1 (1.1)		
Jinkfuin	2 (0.9)	2 (1.9)			2 (0.9)	2 (1.9)			3 (1.2)	1 (1.1)		
Kikfuini	46 (20.8)	17 (15.7)			49 (21.6)	15 (14.6)			54 (22.2)	10 (11.5)		
Konene	1 (0.5)	0 (0)			1 (0.4)	0 (0)			1 (0.4)	0 (0)		
Ngwa	3 (1.4)	25 (23.1)			3 (1.3)	25 (24.3)			14 (5.8)	14 (16.1)		
Marital status												
Married	141 (63.8)	55 (50.9)	8.753	0.033	145 (63.9)	51 (49.5)	9.654	0.022	151 (62.1)	45 (51.7)	11.308	0.010
Single	72 (32.6)	52 (48.1)			74 (32.6)	51 (49.5)			85 (35.0)	40 (46.0)		
Divorced	2 (0.9)	0 (0)			2 (0.9)	0 (0)			0 (0)	2 (2.3)		

Widow	6 (2.7)	1 (0.9)			6 (2.6)	1 (1.0)			7 (2.9)	0 (0)		
Education												
NFE	53 (24.0)	7 (6.5)	17.498	0.001	52 (22.9)	8 (7.8)	21.304	0.000	54 (22.2)	6 (6.9)	20.706	0.000
Primary	74 (33.5)	50 (46.3)			73 (32.2)	52 (50.5)			86 (35.4)	39 (44.8)		
Secondary	86 (38.9)	43 (39.8)			95 (41.9)	34 (33.0)			97 (39.9)	32 (36.8)		
Tertiary	8 (3.6)	8 (7.4)			7 (3.1)	9 (8.7)			6 (2.5)	10 (11.5)		